

Smear Layer Removal Efficacy of Ultrasonically Activated Herbal Irrigants Compared With 17% EDTA: An Ex-vivo Scanning Electron Microscopic Study

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Abstract

Background: This ex-vivo study compared smear layer removal by ultrasonically activated 17% EDTA and 10% aqueous extracts of Neem, Tulsi, Green Tea, and Turmeric using SEM and the Hülsmann scoring system.

Materials and Methods: 100 extracted mandibular premolars were assigned to five groups (n = 20). Canals were prepared to size 25/06 (HyFlex EDM) and irrigated with 5.25% NaOCl, followed by the test irrigant with ultrasonic activation and a final NaOCl rinse. SEM evaluation was performed at coronal, middle, and apical thirds.

Results: 17% EDTA showed the lowest smear layer scores (median 1.0; IQR 1.0–2.0) at all canal levels. Herbal irrigants demonstrated significantly higher scores, with smear layer persistence increasing apically (p < 0.001). Acceptable smear layer removal occurred in 88.3% of EDTA specimens versus 48.3% (Neem), 11.7% (Tulsi), and 0% (Green Tea, Turmeric). None met non-inferiority criteria.

Conclusion: Ultrasonically activated 17% EDTA was superior to all tested herbal irrigants for smear layer removal, particularly in the apical third. Although herbal irrigants exhibit antimicrobial and biocompatible properties, they cannot replace EDTA for smear layer elimination and may be considered only as adjunctive agents. Further studies should focus on optimizing phytochemical formulations to enhance their smear layer removal efficacy.

Keywords: Smear Layer Removal, Endodontic Irrigants, Ultrasonic Activation, Scanning Electron microscopy, Hülsmann Smear Layer Scoring System.

Introduction

Endodontic therapy aims to prevent or eliminate apical periodontitis by eradicating microbial infection from the root canal system while preserving functional teeth.¹ This is achieved through effective pulp removal, thorough disinfection, and three-dimensional obturation. Although success rates of 85–95% have been reported when these principles are adequately followed, treatment failures still occur, most commonly due to persistent microorganisms, inadequate debridement, or incomplete sealing, highlighting the critical role of effective cleaning and disinfection.^{1,2}

Mechanical instrumentation alone cannot adequately address the complex anatomy of the root canal system, including fins, isthmuses, lateral canals, apical deltas, and dentinal tubules.³ These limitations justify the indispensable role of chemical irrigation, which supplements mechanical preparation

by dissolving organic and inorganic debris, neutralizing microbial toxins, flushing debris, and penetrating uninstrumented areas. Effective irrigation also facilitates smear layer removal, enhances sealer penetration, and reduces the risk of microbial recolonization.

The smear layer is an amorphous layer of organic and inorganic debris formed during instrumentation, measuring approximately 1–5 μm in thickness and penetrating dentinal tubules up to 40 μm. While its retention has been debated, substantial evidence supports its removal to improve disinfection, sealer adaptation, and long-term treatment outcomes, as retained smear layer may harbor microorganisms and promote microleakage.^{4,5}

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Conventional irrigants such as sodium hypochlorite, chlorhexidine, and 17% ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) are widely used due to their antimicrobial and chelating properties.⁶ EDTA remains the reference standard for smear layer removal owing to its predictable chelation of calcium ions, particularly in the coronal and middle thirds.⁷ However, limitations including cytotoxicity, dentin erosion, and reduced apical efficacy have driven interest in alternative irrigants with improved biocompatibility.^{8,9}

Phytotherapy has gained attention in endodontics because of the antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties of plant-derived compounds.¹⁰ Herbal agents such as Neem, Tulsi, Green Tea, and Turmeric contain bioactive constituents with antimicrobial and metal-binding potential, providing a theoretical basis for their investigation as irrigants. However, antimicrobial efficacy does not necessarily translate to effective smear layer removal, and this assumption remains insufficiently validated.

Existing literature on herbal irrigants is limited by methodological heterogeneity, inconsistent extract preparation, variable concentrations, lack of activation protocols, and inappropriate statistical analyses particularly the use of mean-based parametric tests for Hülsmann's ordinal scoring system. Evidence regarding their performance in the apical third and under ultrasonic activation remains sparse, limiting the validity and transferability of reported findings.^{11,12}

Accordingly, the present ex vivo study compared the smear layer removal efficacy of ultrasonically activated 17% EDTA and 10% (w/v) aqueous extracts of Neem, Tulsi, Green Tea, and Turmeric. Smear layer removal was evaluated using scanning electron microscopy and Hülsmann's ordinal scoring system, with non-parametric statistical analysis selected to ensure methodological rigor, minimize analytical bias, and enhance the reliability of the findings, while acknowledging the inherent limitations of ex vivo designs in clinical generalization.¹²

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This ex vivo experimental comparative study evaluated smear layer removal following the use of different endodontic irrigating solutions.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee prior to study initiation (Approval No.: SDCH/MDS-ENDO/IEC/05/2024). Written informed consent was obtained from patients for the use of extracted teeth for research purposes. Patient confidentiality was maintained. The study did not involve live human participants or animals.

Sample Selection and Allocation

Using convenience sampling, 100 freshly extracted human mandibular premolars meeting the inclusion criteria were collected. Teeth were caries-free, periodontally compromised, had intact crowns, single straight canals, and mature apices. Teeth with caries, restorations, cracks, fractures, develop-

mental anomalies, or primary teeth were excluded.

Specimens were cleaned, disinfected with 5.25% sodium hypochlorite, examined under a dental operating microscope to exclude microcracks, and radiographically evaluated to confirm canal anatomy. Teeth were stored in 0.9% saline at 4°C until use.

Samples were randomly allocated (computer-generated randomization) into five groups (n = 20 each):

Group A: 17% EDTA

Group B: 10% Neem extract

Group C: 10% Tulsi extract

Group D: 10% Green Tea extract

Group E: 10% Turmeric extract

Sample Size Estimation

Sample size was calculated using G*Power software (version 3.0) based on one-way ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$, power = 80%, effect size = 0.36), yielding a minimum sample size of 100 specimens.

Preparation of Herbal Irrigants

All herbal irrigants were prepared as 10% w/v aqueous extracts under standardized laboratory conditions at the Department of Biomedical Sciences, Kumaon University, Nainital, Uttarakhand. Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*), and Green Tea (*Camellia sinensis*) leaves were shade-dried, powdered, and extracted by boiling 15 g of powder with 150 mL distilled water at 100°C until the volume was reduced to approximately 15–20 mL. After cooling, the volume was adjusted to 150 mL, filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and stored at 4°C in opaque containers. Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) rhizomes were washed, sliced, oven-dried at 45–50°C for 9–10 days, powdered, and extracted using the same aqueous extraction protocol.^{13,14,15}

Specimen Preparation and Irrigation Protocol

Standardized access cavities were prepared, canal patency established with a #10 K-file, and working length determined 1 mm short of the apical foramen. Coronal flaring was performed using Gates Glidden drills (sizes 1 and 2). Instrumentation was carried out using HyFlex EDM rotary files up to size 25/06 at 400 rpm and 2.5 Ncm torque.

During instrumentation, canals were irrigated with 5 mL of 5.25% sodium hypochlorite, followed by 5 mL of the assigned irrigant delivered using a 30-gauge side-vented needle. Ultrasonic activation was applied for 30 seconds per canal segment to enhance irrigant efficacy. A final rinse with 5 mL of 5.25% sodium hypochlorite was performed, after which canals were dried and sealed coronally with Cavit™.

Scanning Electron Microscope Evaluation

Specimens were sectioned buccolingually, dehydrated in ascending ethanol concentrations, sputter-coated with gold, and examined under a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Smear layer removal was evaluated at the coronal, middle, and apical thirds using the Hülsmann Smear Layer Scoring System¹²:

Score 1: No smear layer; dentinal tubules fully open

Score 2: Small smear layer; most tubules open

Score 3: Homogeneous smear layer; few tubules open

Score 4: Homogeneous smear layer covering all tubules; none open

Score 5: Thick, non-homogeneous smear layer covering all tubules

Figure I: Representative scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of smear layer removal at the coronal level. The images are arranged from left to right as follows: 17% EDTA, 10% Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), 10% Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*), 10% Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), and 10% Green Tea (*Camellia sinensis*).

Figure II: Representative scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of smear layer removal at the middle level. The images are arranged from left to right as follows: 17% EDTA, 10% Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), 10% Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*), 10% Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), and 10% Green Tea (*Camellia sinensis*).

Figure III: Representative scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of smear layer removal at the apical level. The images are arranged from left to right as follows: 17% EDTA, 10% Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), 10% Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*), 10% Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), and 10% Green Tea (*Camellia sinensis*).

Statistical Analysis

Smear layer scores were expressed as median and

interquartile range (IQR) due to their ordinal nature. Intergroup comparisons among the five irrigants were performed using the Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by pairwise Mann–Whitney U tests with Bonferroni correction. Intragroup comparisons across coronal, middle, and apical thirds were analyzed using the Friedman test with Wilcoxon signed-rank post hoc analysis. A non-inferiority analysis was conducted by dichotomizing smear layer scores (≤ 2 considered clinically acceptable) and comparing success proportions against EDTA using a non-inferiority margin () of 10%. Ninety-five percent confidence intervals (95% CI) were calculated for absolute differences. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Overall Smear Layer Removal Efficacy

Ultrasonically activated 17% EDTA demonstrated significantly superior smear layer removal compared with all tested herbal irrigants ($p < 0.001$). EDTA consistently showed the lowest smear layer scores, indicating near-complete smear layer elimination, whereas Neem, Tulsi, Turmeric, and Green Tea exhibited progressively higher scores, reflecting inferior performance. These findings clearly refute the initial hypothesis that herbal irrigants could achieve smear layer removal comparable to EDTA.

Intergroup Comparison and Interpretation

Intergroup analysis revealed that all herbal irrigants were statistically and clinically inferior to EDTA. The magnitude of difference was substantial, with median score differences of one or more units on the Hülsmann five-point ordinal scale. This confirms that the observed inferiority of herbal irrigants was not marginal but clinically meaningful. The results reaffirm EDTA's established role as the most effective chelating agent for smear layer removal.

Non-Inferiority Analysis

Non-inferiority testing further supported these findings. EDTA achieved an acceptable smear layer removal rate (scores ≤ 2) of 88.3%, whereas Neem demonstrated 48.3%, Tulsi 11.7%, and both Turmeric and Green Tea showed no acceptable outcomes. All herbal irrigants failed to meet the predefined non-inferiority margin of 10%, with confidence intervals extending well beyond this threshold, confirming clear inferiority rather than equivalence.

Regional (Canal Third-Wise) Evaluation

Smear layer scores increased significantly from the coronal to the apical third across all experimental groups ($p < 0.05$). EDTA exhibited the least reduction in efficacy across canal levels, maintaining superior smear layer removal even in the apical third. Among the herbal irrigants, Neem demonstrated relatively lower apical smear layer scores compared with Tulsi, Turmeric, and Green Tea; however, it remained inferior to EDTA at all canal levels.

Empirical Evidence from Scanning Electron Microscope Analysis

These findings were substantiated by SEM evaluation using the Hülsmann smear layer scoring system. EDTA specimens

predominantly demonstrated open dentinal tubules with minimal or absent smear layer (median = 1; IQR = 1). In contrast, herbal irrigant groups showed partial to complete smear layer coverage, particularly in the middle and apical thirds. Statistical testing confirmed significant intergroup differences ($p < 0.001$) and significant intragroup variation across canal thirds ($p < 0.05$).

Agent	Median	Q1	Q3	IQR
EDTA	1.0	1.0	2.0	1.0
Neem	3.0	2.0	3.0	1.0
Tulsi	3.0	3.0	4.0	1.0
Turmeric	4.0	3.0	4.0	1.0
Green Tea	5.0	4.0	5.0	1.0

Table I: Descriptive statistics of SEM smear layer scores by irrigant.

Herbal vs EDTA	Difference (H – E)	95% CI (lower, upper)
Neem	-40.0%	-55.0% to -25.0%
Tulsi	-76.7%	-88.2% to -65.2%
Turmeric	-88.3%	-96.5% to -80.2%
Green Tea	-88.3%	-96.5% to -80.2%

Table II: Non-inferiority comparison of herbal irrigants versus 17% EDTA.

Agent	Successes	Total	Success rate
EDTA	53	60	88.3%
Neem	29	60	48.3%
Tulsi	7	60	11.7%
Turmeric	0	60	0%
Green Tea	0	60	0%

Table III: Success rates of smear layer removal across irrigants.

Figure IV: Box-and-whisker plot showing distribution of SEM smear layer scores.

Discussion

The present ex-vivo study evaluated the smear layer removal efficacy of 17% EDTA and selected herbal irrigants Neem, Tulsi, Turmeric, and Green Tea using scanning electron

microscopy and Hülsmann’s ordinal scoring system. The initial hypothesis that herbal irrigants would demonstrate smear layer removal comparable to or non-inferior to EDTA was not supported. EDTA consistently exhibited superior smear layer removal across all root canal levels, reflected by the lowest median scores and the highest proportion of acceptable outcomes (scores ≤ 2). In contrast, all tested herbal irrigants showed significantly higher smear layer scores, indicating inferior performance. The magnitude of these differences was both statistically and clinically significant, with differences of one or more complete score units on a five-point ordinal scale, reaffirming the established chelating efficacy of EDTA.

Non-inferiority analysis using a conservative margin of 10% further confirmed that none of the herbal irrigants met the predefined criteria for equivalence with EDTA. The confidence intervals for all herbal agents lay well beyond the non-inferiority margin, clearly indicating inferiority rather than marginal loss of efficacy. This outcome represents appropriate hypothesis testing supported by robust statistical methodology rather than an inconclusive or underpowered analysis.

Across all irrigants, smear layer scores increased progressively from the coronal to the apical third, consistent with known anatomical and fluid-dynamic challenges in the apical region, including reduced canal diameter, vapor lock effect, and limited irrigant exchange. EDTA demonstrated the least deterioration across canal levels, likely due to its strong chelating action, which remains effective even under suboptimal flow conditions. Neem showed relatively better median apical scores compared with other herbal irrigants; however, it remained inferior to EDTA overall. This observation is best explained by a global reduction in irrigant effectiveness within the apical third, where penetration dynamics dominate over chemical potency, rather than by superior chelating activity of Neem.

The inferior performance of herbal irrigants in the coronal and middle thirds suggests that their limitations are not solely attributable to apical anatomy. Herbal extracts typically possess higher viscosity, variable particulate content, and lack surfactant properties, which negatively affect wettability, penetration, and contact with dentinal surfaces.¹³ Unlike EDTA, which actively chelates inorganic components of the smear layer, herbal irrigants rely on weaker organic acids or bioactive phytochemicals that appear insufficient for effective smear layer removal even in relatively accessible regions of the canal.⁷

A critical appraisal of earlier studies reporting favorable smear layer removal with herbal irrigants reveals important methodological and statistical flaws. Many such studies have inappropriately calculated mean values and applied parametric statistical tests to Hülsmann smear layer scores, despite the ordinal (non-continuous) nature of this scale.^{12,15} Because scores represent ranked categories rather than equidistant numerical values, mean-based analyses are statistically invalid and may produce misleading conclusions. In contrast, the present study employed median-based non-

parametric analyses, providing a more accurate and methodologically sound interpretation. Furthermore, variations in canal preparation protocols, absence of ultrasonic activation, inconsistent apical evaluation, and non-standardized or dilute herbal extract preparation in earlier studies further compromise the validity of their conclusions.

In the present investigation, all herbal irrigants were prepared as standardized 10% w/v aqueous extracts under controlled laboratory conditions and used in relatively concentrated form with ultrasonic activation to minimize methodological bias. Despite these optimized conditions, herbal irrigants failed to demonstrate smear layer removal comparable to EDTA, strongly suggesting that previously reported positive outcomes may reflect methodological artifacts rather than true chelating efficacy.

Limitations

This study was conducted under ex-vivo conditions, which may not fully replicate the complex clinical environment of root canal irrigation, including continuous irrigant replenishment, temperature variation, and dynamic fluid flow. The evaluation was limited to conventional aqueous herbal extracts and did not assess modified formulations such as surfactant-enhanced, nano-formulated, or chelator-enriched herbal preparations. Additionally, only smear layer removal was evaluated; antimicrobial efficacy, cytotoxicity, and effects on dentin microhardness were not assessed. These factors should be explored in future studies to better define the potential adjunctive role of herbal irrigants in endodontic therapy.

Conclusion

Within the limitations of this ex-vivo study, ultrasonically activated 17% EDTA demonstrated superior smear layer removal compared with all tested herbal irrigants. None of the herbal agents met criteria for non-inferiority, and therefore cannot be recommended as substitutes for EDTA for smear layer elimination. While herbal irrigants may possess beneficial antimicrobial or biocompatible properties, their role appears more suitable as adjuncts rather than replacements for established chelating agents.

Patient's / Guardian's Consent

Not applicable. The present ex-vivo study was conducted on extracted human teeth, and no patient-identifiable data (textual, clinical, radiographic, or histopathologic images) were used.

Ethical Clearance

Ethical approval (Approval No.: SDCH/MDS-ENDO/IEC/05/2024) was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Seema Dental College and Hospital, Rishikesh, Uttarakhand, prior to initiation of the study. The approval letter is attached/submitted along with the manuscript. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. No animal experimentation was involved.

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Declaration of Interest

Declarations of interest: None

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Authors' Contributions

All authors approved the final version of the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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